

5 Reasons why IoT is not yet on top of retailers' minds?

- By Nigam Shah

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In the year 2017, the buzzword – internet of things has managed to reach maximum ears, with increasing talks in the media. As the term floats around, it takes a while to believe that this is not limited to talks but also actually happening.

A very traditional industry – retail, where few percentage of customers still believe in tangibility of product, retailers have barely explored the IoT zone. Though, market researchers predict the gains upto 95 billion by 2025.

Amazon as always are breaking the boundaries through another great step of grocery stores without checkouts. Now, retailers are left with assumptions that -is this another marketing stunt or do the business benefit from such strategies. As a result of this, the adoption rate is slowed down. However, this can be worked it out if retailers are provided necessary information. It can help them to identify the right path and overcome the difficulties their businesses are already facing due to the increasing role of eCommerce.

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Whereas, there are no signs of the slowdown looking to the pace of evolution that comes with the era of IoT. Then why IoT is not yet on top of retailers' minds even though with such a great abundance of solutions in the market?

Here's what we think as potential reasons:

1. Retailers are yet unknown with IoT and its magic

No doubts, retailers are open for discussion about innovation, but when it comes to implementation, the decision makers take a step behind and hesitate to leave the traditional methods of doing business. At present, they can feel being wise and playing safe but in near future this can turn to biggest mistake. The competition will remain at peak as always and customer being digitally fascinated beings can swap you with other at any point. Start providing better or more personalized and secure your future business. Let the first step begin to change the belief and remove the hesitation.

2. Throughout excelled service from online to offline is a challenge

Consumer habits are changing along with the fascinating rise of eCommerce. It is now no-longer unknown fact that mobile usage have replaced the desktop. The further transition from mobile can be towards IoT. Therefore, smoothing out the offline processes of delivery, cancellation and returns and further click-and-collect would definitely make the future transition to IoT effortless.

3. High expectation on immediate results

The nature of IoT is it brings results over a period of time. Retailers are testing the IoT solutions and expect immediate results, which are not easily achievable. Also, you need to understand that a single layer of IoT solutions will not work. The integration should cover all aspects of business. Ex. Implementing inventory management only will not give remarkable results. Along with this you need to to start with the very basics and utilise the diverse capabilities of automation technology for connecting with other tools.

4. Unsure about the security and privacy

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Security and privacy of consumers and retailers are the cream topics that are published across media. The possibility of risks and breaches are the areas of worries where they give a second thought before applying it. The more connected devices are out there, the higher chance of threat they assume.

5. How to start and where to start

Rather than getting lost in the ocean it would be smart to start with easy accessible solutions. Ex. the sensors customers are already carrying in the mobile phones, the real-time data on offline customer behaviour. Customer delight is sure-shot first step towards setting up an IoT environment.

- Increasing staff costs,
- Higher lease rates,
- Ever growing role of eCommerce

These all are very clear indicators for retailers they are likely to face a number of challenges in the near future, if they do not become active about it. And this is getting proved from the difficulties arising inevitably leading to stores closing down.

Gateway Technolabs advises not to fear or hesitate about the implementation of IoT solutions. Gateway has provided [automotive management services](#) to many European car manufacturers with IoT enabled applications. Initiate the process that map best with your business priorities to sustain in market for now and for coming future. Meanwhile, we'll be happy to chat or provide consultation more on the topic of retail IoT. Feel free to write us at germany@gatewaytechnolabs.com or get in touch anytime at +4971189989145!